

Inhibitive action of 1-hydroxyethylenedine-1,1-diphosphonic acid antiscalant towards corrosion of carbon steel in cooling water system

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Abstract : 1-Hydroxyethylenedine-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP) has been used as antiscalant as well as corrosion inhibitor in cooling water system (CWS) in presence and absence of zinc ions. Weight loss, electrochemical polarization and metallurgical research microscopy technique have been carried out at different temperatures and concentrations of the inhibitor. Mechanism of inhibition has been explained on the basis of molecular structure and the inhibitor provides a good inhibition efficiency and acts as anodic inhibitor when present alone and as mixed inhibitor in presence of zinc ions. However, addition of zinc ions to CWS along with HEDP, do not increase inhibition efficiency of inhibitor to an appreciable extent.

Keywords : Corrosion inhibitors, antiscalant, cooling water system, carbon steel, HEDP.

Introduction

It is common practice to use antiscalants, like phosphates, polyphosphates¹⁻⁶, organophosphonates⁷⁻¹⁴ etc., corrosion inhibitors, dispersants, biocides, pH boosters and hardness stabilizers in industrial CWS. Addition of various chemicals to the CWS makes the cooling water chemistry very complex and complicated that it is very difficult to control and understand the chemistry of cooling water by the operator. A clear understanding about the contribution of antiscalant, corrosion inhibitors and zinc ions separately towards the corrosion control in a CWS is required. The question, whether it is possible to use a single chemical treatment formulation which may act as antiscalant as well as corrosion inhibitor in a CWS has not yet been addressed in the literature. It is also important to make an attempt reduce the chemicals load being added in a CWS. If it is possible to find an antiscalant, which can also provide protection from corrosion in the CWS, it will not only make cooling water chemistry simple but also reduce the operational cost. Zinc ions (cathodic inhibitor) are usually added to the CWS to control the corrosion. A clear understanding about the contribution of antiscalant and zinc ions separately towards the corrosion control in a CWS is required.

Venugopalan and co-workers¹⁵ studied effects of HEDP, gluconate and zinc on the corrosion inhibition of carbon steel. They developed this ternary inhibitor formulation for carbon steel which acts synergistically and gives good corrosion protection for carbon steel. Appa Rao and Srinivas Rao¹⁶ studied ascorbate as a second synergistic with zinc and phosphonate towards corrosion protection of carbon steel in low chloride environment. Results obtained were similar to those obtained by Venugopalan and co-workers. Shibli and co-workers¹⁷ studied influence of HEDP on the corrosion inhibition performance of calcium gluconate on carbon steel and found that addition of HEDP to gluconate increases corrosion inhibition efficiency (CIE) of gluconate to considerable extent. Rajendran *et al.*¹⁸ studied the influence of chloride ions concentration on the CIE of the HEDP-Zn system and found that CIE of HEDP-Zn formulation decrease with increase in chloride ion concentration in water. They also studied the influence of sodium dodecyl sulphate-Zn-HEDP system¹⁹ towards corrosion inhibition of carbon steel and found that this combination gave synergistic effect and provide complete protection in low chloride ion water. Mosayebi and co-workers²⁰ studied the effects of phosphonates based corrosion inhibitors in

CWS. They found that HEDP gives good results towards CIE among various investigated phosphonates.

In the present work, antiscalant, HEDP, has been used as corrosion inhibitors at various concentrations, temperatures and in six different synthetic cooling waters. It has also been investigated whether addition of zinc ions in CWS along with the above mentioned antiscalant is necessary or not to get a good corrosion protection.

Methodology :

Six synthetic cooling waters of different composition used for the corrosion experiments were prepared using A.R. grade chemicals and triple distilled water. The purpose of taking six different compositions of cooling water was the wide range of hardness available in cooling waters in industry depending upon the source of water. Consequently, six different compositions of synthetic cooling water varying from soft to hard water have been prepared for carrying out the experiments. The compositions of all the six synthetic cooling waters have been shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Composition of all the six synthetic cooling waters

Concn. (ppm)	CW I	CW II	CW III	CW IV	CW V	CW VI
Ca ²⁺	75	115	150	200	225	300
Mg ²⁺	24	24	24	24	24	24
HCO ₃ ⁻	305	305	305	305	305	305
CO ₃ ²⁻	30	30	30	30	30	30
Cl ⁻	262	320	430	509	530	692
SO ₄ ²⁻	120	120	120	120	120	120
Na ⁺	253	196	253	251	203	253

Concentration of HEDP used as corrosion inhibitors was changed from 10 ppm to 200 ppm. The experiments were performed at 40, 50 and 60 °C. Influence of addition of zinc ion was also investigated on corrosion rate of carbon steel. Purpose of taking three different temperatures was because of different water temperature at different places in cooling tower. It is hot (~60 °C) in the closed pipes situated near the machineries and cold (~40 °C) near cooling tower and luke warm (~50 °C) at other places.

For weight loss measurements, carbon steel specimens of 3 × 1.5 cm² size were cut from the carbon steel sheet whereas for electrochemical polarization investigations, specimens of size 5 × 1.0 cm² were used. All the speci-

mens were mechanically polished successively with the help of emery papers of grades 100, 200, 300, 400 and 600μ and then thoroughly cleaned with plenty of double distilled water and then with acetone. The specimens were dried with hot air drier and stored in a dessicator over silica gel.

After recording the initial weights of carbon steel specimens on a Mettler Toledo, Japan, AB 135-S/FACT, single pan analytical balance (with a precision of 0.01 mg), they were immersed in tilted position in 250 ml beakers each having 200 ml of synthetic cooling waters as corroding medium with or without the inhibitor. Experiments were carried out in an electronically controlled air thermostat at 40, 50 and 60 °C with in an accuracy of ±0.1 °C. After exposing the specimens for 30 days, the specimens were taken out from the beaker and washed with double distilled water and dried and then weighed again. Corrosion rate in mils per year (mpy) and percentage inhibition efficiency were calculated using the following equations,

$$\text{Corrosion rate (mpy)} = \frac{534 \times W}{DAT} \quad (1)$$

where, W = weight loss (mg), D = density of carbon steel (g/cm³), A = area of specimen (sq. inch), T = exposure time (h).

Electrochemical polarization studies were carried out in 500 ml glass cell having three electrodes system assembly. Potentiostatic polarization of the working electrode was carried out by using a Potentiostat/Galvanostat PGS 201 T (Tacussel, France).

The working electrode was carbon steel under study, platinum electrode was used as counter electrode or an auxiliary electrode. All the potentials were measured against a pencil type Luggin capillary saturated calomel electrode as reference electrode. A Luggin capillary filled with the test solution was used to connect the reference electrode with the cell. The tip of the Luggin capillary was kept very close to the working area of the electrode but without touching it in order to minimize the IR drop and this distance was kept constant during the whole study. Only 1 cm² area of specimen was used as working area and the rest of the area of the specimen was covered with a lacquer except the other tip of specimen which was used for making electrical connection.

Linear polarization resistance measurements were carried out potentiostatically by scanning through a potential range of 14 mV above and below the OCP value in steps of 2 mV. Experiments were carried out in absence and presence of inhibitors at their 200, 150, 100, 80, 60, 40, 20 and 10 ppm concentrations at 40, 50 and 60 °C. The resulting current is plotted against the potential and slope of the line is measured.

The corrosion current, I_{corr} is related to the slope of the line by Stern-Geary equation,

$$\frac{\Delta E}{\Delta i} = \frac{\beta_a \times \beta_c}{2.303 I_{corr} (\beta_a + \beta_c)} \quad (2)$$

where, $\Delta E/\Delta i$ is the slope which is linear polarization resistance (R_p), β_a and β_c are anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes respectively and I_{corr} is the corrosion current density in $\mu A/cm^2$.

The anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes were measured after recording anodic and cathodic polarization curves of the specimen up to a maximum shift of ± 140 mV from OCP value in steps of 10 mV. Experiments were carried out in absence and presence of the inhibitor at their 200, 150, 100, 80, 40, 20 and 10 ppm concentrations at 40, 50 and 60 °C.

Rearranging the above eq. (2),

$$I_{corr} = \frac{\beta_a \times \beta_c}{2.303 I_{corr} (\beta_a + \beta_c)} \times \frac{1}{R_p} \quad (3)$$

The corrosion current density I_{corr} , is related to the corrosion rate by the equation,

$$\text{Corrosion rate (C.R.) (mpy)} = \frac{0.1288 \times I_{corr} \times \text{Eq. Wt.}}{D} \quad (4)$$

where, Eq. Wt. = gram equivalent weight of metal/alloy, D = density of metal (g/cm^3), I_{corr} = corrosion current density ($\mu A/cm^2$).

Results

pH, conductance, total dissolved solids (T.D.S.), P and M alkalinity, total hardness, calcium hardness, Langelier Saturation Index (LSI), ΔG^{21} and Saturation Index (SI)²² were measured for each synthetic cooling water and are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Various parameters of six different synthetic cooling waters

Parameters	CW I	CW II	CW III	CW IV	CW V	CW VI
pH	8.26	8.53	8.26	8.08	8.30	8.08
Conductance	1.54	2.02	2.16	2.30	2.50	2.70
T.D.S.	1027	1347	1440	1534	1667	1800
M-Alkalinity	285	290	300	305	310	320
Ca-hardness	119	182	238	317	357	480
Total hardness	187	287	374	498	560	750
L.S.I. from						
Activity coeff.	1.04	1.14	1.25	1.30	1.35	1.47
ΔG value	1.09	1.10	1.26	1.38	1.48	1.63
S.I. value	0.43	0.54	0.69	0.75	0.83	0.98

Percentage corrosion inhibition efficiency (PCIE) values of HEDP as corrosion inhibitor at various concentrations (10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 150 and 200 ppm) in all the six synthetic cooling waters measured by weight loss method at pH 6.5 and temperature 40, 50 and 60 °C have been shown in Table 3.

Table 3. Percentage corrosion inhibition efficiency of HEDP in all six cooling waters by weight loss method at pH 6.5 and at 40, 50 and 60 °C

Water type	Concn. (ppm)	40 °C	50 °C	60 °C
CW I	10	67.8	45.8	-
	20	71.2	64.9	43.7
	40	74.6	70.2	63.3
	60	84.7	74.7	71.8
	80	89.8	85.7	73.7
	100	96.6	90.6	86.1
	150	-	98.9	91.3
CW II	200	-	-	99.9
	10	55.5	41.8	-
	20	72.2	54.2	42.0
	40	72.2	70.9	55.1
	60	77.8	71.3	71.3
	80	88.9	79.9	72.2
	100	88.9	82.8	81.4
CW III	150	-	89.1	82.9
	200	-	-	90.2
	10	46.8	31.1	-
	20	48.5	45.7	30.5
	40	62.2	47.8	45.2
	60	70.8	60.1	46.9
	80	75.7	71.3	61.6
CW IV	100	81.1	74.9	73.2
	150	-	81.5	75.5
	200	-	-	82.5

Table-3 (contd.)					Table-4 (contd.)					
CW IV	10	42.0	28.1	-	CW III	10	46.8	49.2	52.5	56.1
	20	51.9	40.1	27.1		20	48.5	51.2	55.1	59.0
	40	63.9	53.2	39.6		40	62.2	63.4	66.3	69.4
	60	65.9	65.2	53.4		60	70.8	71.8	75.5	80.1
	80	70.0	66.7	66.4		80	75.9	77.7	80.9	86.3
	100	74.2	71.3	66.8		100	81.1	84.1	87.4	92.0
	150	-	78.9	72.8		150	-	-	95.2	99.9
CW V	200	-	-	80.2	CW IV	10	42.0	42.5	47.2	48.7
	10	25.5	11.1	-		20	51.9	54.2	58.1	60.5
	20	40.3	23.3	10.2		40	63.9	63.7	66.6	69.0
	40	45.6	41.2	24.4		60	65.9	66.0	69.5	73.0
	60	43.7	43.7	42.2		80	70.0	71.6	75.0	79.4
	80	60.3	54.7	44.6		100	74.2	79.6	87.9	87.5
	100	62.2	61.3	55.7		150	-	-	94.7	100.0
CW VI	150	-	65.2	63.4	CW V	10	25.5	27.8	32.8	34.8
	200	-	-	66.9		20	40.3	44.0	52.6	49.9
	10	8.9	5.8	-		40	45.6	47.0	57.1	53.4
	20	13.4	10.9	6.2		60	53.7	56.8	59.2	63.3
	40	13.4	14.4	9.9		80	60.3	62.8	67.2	72.6
	60	17.7	14.4	13.7		100	62.2	66.1	69.3	73.9
	80	32.5	18.7	14.9		150	-	-	80.4	86.5
CW VI	100	48.9	33.5	19.7	CW VI	10	8.9	11.8	14.6	17.8
	150	-	50.9	35.2		20	13.4	18.2	21.9	23.5
	200	-	-	51.5		40	13.4	18.2	23.1	27.7
						60	17.7	22.5	26.6	31.8
						80	32.5	36.8	40.9	45.6
						100	48.9	51.6	56.9	61.0
						150	-	-	70.6	77.1

PCIE of HEDP measured in presence of different concentration of zinc ions from 50 to 150 ppm in all six cooling waters by weight loss method at pH 6.5 and 40 °C have been shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Percentage corrosion inhibition efficiency of HEDP with zinc ions in all the six cooling waters by weight loss method at pH 6.5 and at 40 °C

Water type	HEDP (ppm)	Zn ²⁺			
		0 ppm	50 ppm	100 ppm	200 ppm
CW I	10	67.8	69.1	72.6	76.0
	20	71.2	74.8	78.3	81.7
	40	74.6	77.4	80.6	84.0
	60	84.7	86.3	88.3	90.8
	80	89.8	89.4	92.6	96.0
	100	96.6	98.8	100.0	100.0
CW II	150	-	-	100.0	100.0
	10	5.55	56.6	63.4	67.8
	20	72.2	74.3	79.1	80.2
	40	72.2	73.0	80.6	83.4
	60	77.8	80.6	84.2	88.2
	80	88.9	88.0	90.7	94.9
	100	88.9	90.1	93.0	96.8
150	-	-	98.5	100.0	

In our earlier research article²³, we have published a new technique to find antiscaling efficiency of different antiscalants at various concentrations in all the six synthetic cooling waters. Antiscaling efficiency of HEDP at various concentrations in synthetic cooling water III and VI has been shown in Table 5 only for the sake of comparison of antiscaling efficiency of HEDP with corrosion inhibition efficiency.

Various corrosion parameters like OCP (open circuit potential), β_a (anodic Tafel slope), β_c (cathodic Tafel slope), R_p (polarization resistance), i_{corr} (critical current density), corrosion rate and percentage inhibition efficiency were calculated from electrochemical polarization experiments for carbon steel in presence of different concentration of HEDP at 40, 50 and 60 °C in CW III and VI and have been shown in Tables 5 and 6 respectively.

The electrochemical data and results obtained with

HEDP as corrosion inhibitor in presence of various concentrations of zinc ions at 40 °C in CW III have been tabulated in Table 7.

Table 5. Percentage antiscaling efficiency of HEDP antiscalant at various concentrations in synthetic cooling water III and VI at 40 °C

Water type	Concentration of HEDP (ppm)	% Antiscaling efficiency
CW III	2	61.2
	5	66.6
	10	67.0
	15	67.3
	20	68.5
CW VI	2	20.0
	5	30.3
	10	33.3
	15	38.3
	20	43.3

Cathodic and anodic polarization curves of carbon steel in synthetic cooling waters III in absence and presence of 10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 150 and 200 ppm HEDP at 40 °C have been shown in Fig. 1. Cathodic and anodic polarization curves of carbon steel in synthetic cooling waters III in absence and presence of 10, 20, 40, 60, 80, 100, 150 and 200 ppm HEDP along with 100 ppm zinc ions at 40 °C have been shown in Fig. 2.

For the surface study of corroded carbon steel samples, inverted trinocular metallurgical research microscope from Getner, Japan, was used in cooling water III and VI after 30 days of exposure in presence and in absence of inhibitor, and have been shown in Fig. 3.

Discussion

The selection of corrosion inhibitor is carried out on the basis of several parameters like cost of corrosion in-

Table 6. Various corrosion parameters calculated from electrochemical experiments for carbon steel in CW III in presence of different concentrations of HEDP at 40, 50 and 60 °C

Concentration of inhibitor (ppm)	Temp. (°C)	OCP (-mV)	β_a (mV/dec)	β_c /decade	R_p ($\Omega \times 10^3$)	I_{corr} ($\mu A/cm^2$)	Corrosion rate (mpy)	% Inhibition efficiency by LPR	% Inhibition efficiency by weight loss
Blank	40	710	130	300	2.77	14.2	6.5	-	-
	50	694	102	282	2.94	14.9	6.8	-	-
	60	685	98	278	1.94	16.2	7.3	-	-
10	40	696	134	236	4.95	7.5	3.4	47.4	46.8
20	40	690	132	248	5.12	7.3	3.3	48.8	48.5
40	40	682	124	230	6.60	5.3	2.4	63.1	62.2
60	40	672	120	262	8.71	4.1	1.9	72.3	70.8
80	40	664	118	296	10.77	3.4	1.6	76.9	75.9
100	40	660	122	270	14.03	2.6	1.2	83.1	81.1
10	50	687	128	248	3.59	10.2	4.7	30.8	31.1
20	50	685	130	262	4.65	8.1	3.7	45.6	45.7
40	50	682	140	265	5.16	7.7	3.5	48.5	47.8
60	50	678	132	266	6.49	5.9	2.7	60.2	60.1
80	50	675	122	308	9.03	4.2	1.9	72.0	71.3
100	50	673	134	302	10.89	3.7	1.7	75.0	74.9
150	50	671	114	300	13.28	2.7	1.2	82.3	81.5
20	60	663	84	210	2.3	11.3	5.0	31.5	30.5
40	60	659	82	208	2.9	8.8	3.9	46.5	45.2
60	60	652	86	240	3.3	8.4	3.7	49.3	46.9
80	60	648	84	238	4.5	6.0	2.6	64.3	61.6
100	60	646	86	206	6.1	4.3	1.9	73.9	73.2
150	60	642	84	220	6.8	3.9	1.7	76.7	75.5
200	60	642	96	206	10.1	2.8	1.2	83.5	82.5

Table 7. Various corrosion parameters calculated from electrochemical experiments for carbon steel in CW VI in presence of different concentrations of HEDP at 40, 50 and 60 °C

Concentration of inhibitor (ppm)	Temp. (°C)	OCP (-mV)	β_a (mV/decade)	β_c (mV/decade)	R_p ($\Omega \times 10^3$)	I_{corr} ($\mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$)	Corrosion rate (mpy)	% Inhibition efficiency by LPR	% Inhibition efficiency by weight loss
Blank	40	690	92	206	1.01	27.4	12.6	-	-
	50	704	82	310	0.97	28.8	13.3	-	-
	60	716	80	220	0.84	30.3	14.0	-	-
10	40	672	120	297	1.50	24.7	11.4	9.5	8.9
20	40	668	120	297	1.58	23.4	10.8	14.3	13.4
40	40	664	120	297	1.63	22.7	10.4	17.4	13.4
60	40	661	120	297	1.68	22.1	10.2	19.0	17.7
80	40	655	98	297	1.76	18.2	8.4	33.3	32.5
100	40	646	130	298	2.89	13.6	6.3	50.0	48.9
10	50	684	104	350	1.29	27.0	12.5	6.0	5.8
20	50	680	104	355	1.37	25.5	11.7	12.0	10.9
40	50	676	116	352	1.40	24.4	11.2	15.7	14.4
60	50	672	132	352	1.71	24.4	11.2	15.7	14.4
80	50	667	132	354	1.78	23.4	10.8	18.7	18.7
100	50	660	130	358	2.18	19.0	8.7	34.5	33.5
150	50	658	130	360	2.96	14.0	6.5	51.1	50.9
20	60	690	88	303	1.04	28.4	13.1	6.4	6.2
40	60	686	88	305	1.08	27.3	12.6	10.0	9.9
60	60	680	88	301	1.13	26.0	12.0	14.2	13.7
80	60	678	88	303	1.15	25.8	11.9	15.0	14.9
100	60	672	88	304	1.22	24.2	11.1	20.7	19.7
150	60	668	136	330	2.18	19.2	8.8	37.1	35.2
200	60	663	138	345	2.95	14.5	6.6	52.8	51.5

hibitor, their availability, solubility in corroding system, and compatibility with other constituents of corroding system, mechanism of action of inhibitor, physical properties and toxicity of the inhibitor²⁴⁻²⁶. Corrosion inhibitors are classified mainly according to the medium of corroding metal such as acidic medium, alkaline, neutral, cooling water and atmospheric medium^{27,28}.

HEDP is a good corrosion inhibitor and in prevents corrosion almost completely in CW I. CIE increases with increase in concentration of HEDP. The PCIE decreases appreciably when chloride ion concentration is increased from CW I to CW VI. A similar trend was observed at a higher temperature of 50 and 60 °C (Table 3).

It is evident from the Table 3 that PCIE decreases with increase in temperature from 40 to 60 °C. At 60 °C in CW I, HEDP gives 99.9% CIE at 200 ppm concentra-

tion. At 40 °C in CW I, 96.6% CIE is provided by HEDP at 100 ppm concentration.

It was observed that PCIE increases with increase of concentration of HEDP from 10 to 100 ppm, decreases with increase of temperature of cooling waters from 40 to 60 °C and decreases with the increase of chloride ion concentration in synthetic cooling waters. HEDP was found to give high CIE at 100 ppm concentration at 40 and 50 °C. A rise of 20 °C in temperature of cooling water requires nearly double concentration of HEDP for achieving the same protection from corrosion.

It is clear from Table 4 that, PCIE increases slightly with increase in concentration of zinc ions in all the six synthetic cooling water. PCIE of HEDP (40 ppm) in cooling water I with out zinc ions was 74.6 but with 200 ppm zinc ions its efficiency increased to 84.0. PCIE of HEDP

Fig. 1. Polarization curve of carbon steel in CW III in absence and presence of different concentrations of HEDP at 40 °C and 6.5 pH.

Fig. 2. Polarization curve of carbon steel in CW III in absence and presence of different concentrations of HEDP along with 100 ppm Zn²⁺ ions at 40 °C and 6.5 pH.

(a) Carbon steel sample blank kept in CW VI for 30 days at 40 °C and 6.5 pH
 (b) Carbon steel sample blank kept in CW III for 30 days at 40 °C and 6.5 pH

(c) Carbon steel sample kept in CW VI for 30 days with 100 ppm HEDP at 40 °C at 6.5 pH
 (c) Carbon steel sample kept in CW III for 30 days with 100 ppm HEDP at 40 °C at 6.5 pH

Fig. 3. Metallurgical micrographs of carbon steel samples when exposed to CW III and VI for 30 days with and without inhibitor.

(100 ppm) in cooling water VI with out zinc ions was 48.9 but with 200 ppm zinc ions its efficiency increased to 61.0. It is very much clear that addition of 200 ppm zinc ions to the cooling water do not increase the CIE of HEDP, appreciably.

OCP value increases in presence of HEDP and this change increases with increase in concentration of HEDP and temperature of the cooling water. Anodic and cathodic Tafel slopes decreases in presence of HEDP, however, the decrease in anodic Tafel slope is quite large. Tafel slopes values changes slightly with increase in concentration of HEDP at all the investigated temperatures. This slight change in Tafel slope values with concentration of HEDP is not of any significance considering the mechanism of inhibition. Linear polarization resistance (R_p) increases appreciably when the concentration of HEDP is sufficient to provide high CIE. Anodic Tafel slope, cathodic Tafel slope and R_p decreases with the change in quality of cooling water from CW III to CW VI. OCP and corrosion rate increased with increase in chloride ion concentration from CW III to CW VI. On adding zinc ions to CW III already having HEDP, the anodic and cathodic Tafel slope increased suggesting that zinc ions influence both anodic and cathodic reactions.

Table 8. Various corrosion parameters calculated from electrochemical experiments for carbon steel in CW III in presence of different concentrations of HEDP with zinc ions at 40 °C

Concentration of inhibitor (ppm)	Zinc ion (ppm)	OCP (-mV)	β_a (mV/decade)	β_c (mV/decade)	R_p ($\Omega \times 10^3$)	I_{corr} ($\mu A/cm^2$)	Corrosion rate (mpy)	% Inhibition efficiency by LPR	% Inhibition efficiency by weight loss
Blank	-	710	130	300	2.77	14.2	6.5	-	-
10	50	682	146	256	5.65	7.1	3.3	49.2	47.6
20	50	678	146	256	6.01	6.7	3.0	53.8	49.6
40	50	672	144	254	8.01	5.0	2.2	66.1	62.2
60	50	670	146	272	10.57	3.9	1.8	72.3	70.9
80	50	666	136	280	13.25	3.0	1.3	80.0	76.9
100	50	662	150	282	19.68	2.16	0.9	86.1	83.7
10	100	686	134	258	5.89	6.5	3.0	53.8	52.5
20	100	682	132	272	6.14	6.28	2.8	56.9	55.1
40	100	678	134	300	8.84	4.55	2.0	68.1	66.3
60	100	674	134	298	1.66	3.44	1.5	76.9	75.5
80	100	670	135	296	15.02	2.68	1.2	81.5	80.9
100	100	668	132	280	22.51	1.73	0.7	89.2	87.4
150	100	664	130	270	176.5	0.65	0.3	95.3	95.2
10	200	682	132	314	6.66	6.06	2.9	55.4	56.1

Table-8 (contd.)

20	200	676	130	312	7.07	5.63	2.5	61.5	59.0
40	200	672	140	313	9.77	4.3	1.9	70.8	69.4
60	200	670	142	350	15.72	2.79	1.2	81.5	80.1
80	200	666	140	345	22.52	1.92	0.8	87.6	86.3
100	200	662	142	360	39.48	1.12	0.5	92.3	92.0
150	200	660	140	365	219.6	0.02	0.09	98.6	99.9

From the polarization curves, it is clear that both anodes and cathodes are polarized with the addition of HEDP in cooling waters, however, anodic polarization is more than cathodic polarization. So, HEDP acts mainly as anodic inhibitor. It is also clear from the polarization curve that, the extent of polarization increases with increase in concentration of HEDP in cooling water. Addition of zinc ions to the cooling water along with HEDP, slightly increase both anodic and cathodic polarization and hence zinc-HEDP combination acts as mixed mode of inhibitor. The addition of zinc ions shifts the corrosion current density towards lower current density value and this trend increases with increase in concentration of zinc ions.

Figs. 3(a) and 3(b) show the micrographs of the corroded surface of carbon steel immersed for 30 days in synthetic cooling water VI (692 ppm chloride ion) and III (262 ppm chloride ion) in absence of HEDP (blank) at 40 °C respectively. Carbon steel surface has been damaged appreciably and pits are clearly visible in Fig. 3(a) when exposed to synthetic cooling water VI. The surface of the specimen in Fig. 3(b) is also heavily corroded though the clear pits are not visible as in case of Fig. 3(a). The addition of 100 ppm HEDP to the CW VI and CW III provides excellent corrosion protection to carbon steel at 40 °C as is clear from the micrographs shown in Figs. 3(c) and 3(d) respectively. The adsorbed film of the inhibitor present on the surface of carbon steel in presence of 100 ppm of HEDP appears to be uniform and covering the carbon steel surface almost completely.

Mechanism of corrosion inhibition can be explained from the molecular structure of inhibitor molecule^{29,30}. 1-Hydroxyethylenedine-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP) having molecular formula, C₂P₂O₇H₈, has the following molecular structure,

1-Hydroxyethylenedine-1,1-diphosphonic acid (HEDP)

In HEDP, hydroxyl oxygen can not extend its valency beyond two because of absence of vacant *d*-orbitals. As hydroxyl oxygen is already coordinated to carbon and oxygen, hence HEDP can not adsorb through any oxygen atoms of hydroxyl group. So, only possibility of adsorption of HEDP is through two phosphoryl oxygen atoms which exists as oxygen anions due to large difference in electronegativity of phosphorous and oxygen. HEDP forms Fe²⁺-HEDP complex with iron atom of carbon steel with its two phosphoryl oxygens. This complex grows on the surface of carbon steel with increase in concentration of inhibitor and may form continuous film at high concentration.

Conclusions :

- (i) Instead of using too many chemicals simultaneously in CWS, it is possible to use a single chemical treatment formulation which can solve both the problems of scaling and corrosion.
- (ii) HEDP provides both antiscaling as well as good corrosion protection to carbon steel in all the six synthetic cooling waters.
- (iii) Use of zinc ions may be avoided in cooling water as addition of zinc ions always create problems in cooling water system.
- (iv) HEDP act as anodic inhibitor and zinc ions as cathodic inhibitor. Together, zinc and HEDP act as mixed inhibitor.
- (v) HEDP forms Fe²⁺-HEDP complex and this complex grows on the surface of carbon steel with

increase in concentration of inhibitor and may form continuous film at high inhibitor concentration.

- (vi) Results obtained from weight loss and electrochemical polarization study were confirmed by metallurgical micrographs taken for the surface study of corroded samples.

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